

Methods

Participants

Data were collected from 167 same-gender pairs of adults (334 individuals, age: $M = 21.3$ years, $SD = 2.6$ years, 230 females, 29 left-handed) in four conditions (conducted on four different groups of participants): from 40 pairs in the first condition (will be referred to as the *Baseline condition*; 80 individuals, all participants fell into the 18-32 year age range [with all but one participant falling into the 18-30 year age range], $M = 21.4$ years, $SD = 2.6$ years, 60 females, 6 left-handed), from 43 pairs in the second condition (will be referred to as the *Unfamiliar condition*; 86 individuals, all participants fell into the 18-38 year age range [with all but two participants falling into the 18-29 year age range], $M = 21.4$ years, $SD = 3.2$ years, 60 females, 9 left-handed), from 41 pairs in the third condition (will be referred to as the *Unimodal condition*; 82 individuals, all participants fell into the 18-28 year age range, $M = 21.4$ years, $SD = 2.2$ years, 58 females, 9 left-handed), and 43 pairs from the fourth condition (will be referred to as the *Competitive condition*; 86 individuals $M = 21.0$ years, $SD = 2.3$ years, 52 females, 5 left-handed). See Section *Manipulating Familiarity, Modality and Participant Goals* for the description of the conditions.

Participants were randomly assigned to conditions and each pair participated in exactly one condition. Participants did not know each other prior to participating in the study. They were recruited either from university courses or through student employment agencies. In case of university courses, the participation was compensated by credit points. In case of student employment agencies, the participation was financially compensated (approx. 6 euros per hour). Participants gave written informed consent after the aims and features of the experiment were explained to them. The study followed the Declaration of Helsinki guidelines. Ethical approval was granted by the local review board of the Institute of Cognitive Neuroscience and Psychology of the HUN-REN Research Centre for Natural Science (United Ethical Review Committee for Research in Psychology; EPKEB). All participants had normal or corrected-to-normal vision and normal hearing. None of the participants reported any psychological or neurological disorders.

Procedure

The data analyzed in this study were collected as part of a larger study designed to investigate the behavioral and neural dynamics of human face-to-face communication. In all four conditions, pairs of participants performed five main tasks in the following order: an introductory free conversation ("Familiarization Phase"), 2-5 rounds of a computer-mediated communicative game ("Bargaining Game" [BG]; the number depending on how much time was used in the initial rounds), a 15-min unstructured conversation ("Free Conversation"), subjective evaluation of the free conversation, and filling three short personality questionnaires.

After the "Familiarization Phase" based on a set of suggested topics, participants were set up with sensors (see *Materials*) and the sound intensity was set at a comfortable level, separately for the two participants. Following each round of the BG task and the Free Conversation, participants were asked to answer a few questions regarding their subjective experience about the previous conversation (e.g. smoothness of conversation, enjoyment of the task) and how

they perceived the other person (e.g. liking, feeling ‘in-sync’). Before the ‘Free Conversation’ phase, participants received short verbal instruction from an experimenter and they were given a new set of suggested topics (e.g. studying abroad, favourite books, films, TV shows), 7 in total (see Appendix *Procedure* Table A1 for the full list of the suggested topics). Participants were informed that they do not have to go through all of the topics listed and they can also come up with topics of their own.

The total duration of the experiment (including the preparation, the actual measurement, and the closing administration after the measurement) was 4 hours. Only data from the Free Conversation task is reported here. The BG task was reported in a separate paper (Béres et al., 2025), while the personality questionnaires were collected for later analyses. Therefore, these phases of the experimental session will not be described in detail here.

The Bargaining Game (BG)

The BG (Galinsky & Mussweiler, 2001; Valley et al., 2002) is a communicative game where participants are instructed to negotiate the trade of some tokens (sellable items shown by icons on the screen). Their task is to trade the tokens in a way to a) increase their wealth, while b) collecting certain “must-have” tokens. Each round was limited to 15 min duration, but pairs were allowed to finish it earlier upon agreement. Difficulty was increased between successive BG rounds to keep the pair engaged and to assess the effect of difficulty on the measured variables. For further details of the implementation of the BG, see Béres et al., 2025.

Manipulating Familiarity, Modality and Participant Goals

Four different conditions were implemented with each pair participating in only one condition. In the Baseline condition, the two participants had a 15-min introductory conversation with each other (“Familiarization Phase”), received multimodal information during the interactions (could see each other during the game through the camera stream), and played the BG in a cooperative manner (non-zero sum game allowing both participants to reach their goals). Each other condition differed from the Baseline condition in exactly one feature. The Unfamiliar condition differed from the Baseline condition in that the two participants did not meet before the BG, instead, they both had the 15-min Familiarization Phase conversation with one of the experimenters (on the same topics). The Unimodal condition differed from the Baseline condition in that participants could not see each other live through the camera during the interactions. Instead, they saw a static picture of each other. (The picture was taken before the start of the BG by webcam; participants were instructed to show a neutral but friendly face.) The Competitive condition differed from the Baseline condition in the way the BG was implemented: in this version of the game, in each round, one type of must-have token was common between the participants. Further, participants were instructed to try winning by collecting a higher amount of wealth than their partner.

The four conditions along with the multiple rounds of BG enabled experimental manipulation along three dimensions: pre-task familiarity of the interlocutors, modality of communication (unimodal or multimodal), and the compatibility of the participants’ goals (cooperative vs. competitive).

Data Acquisition

All real-time data were recorded by computers with a common time-stamping system implemented through Network Time Protocol on the local-network (~1 ms precision) for collecting them into a coherent data set of continuous measures, which were then supplemented by demographical, evaluation, and psychological test data.

Materials

Participants were equipped with high-density EEG (not analyzed for the current paper), wearable eye tracker, inertial motion capture system, and a headset microphone (Fig. 1). Speech was captured by the headset microphone and played back to the partner from a loudspeaker in the other laboratory. Video of the participant's head was captured by a webcam and shown on-line to the partner (except when a static picture was shown). Audio and video communication was implemented via low-latency streams (180 ms across laboratories). See further details of the equipment and software implementation later in this section and in Appendix *Materials*.

Figure 1. **Sensors used in the BG.**

The participant was equipped with high-density EEG, wearable eye tracker, inertial motion capture system, and headset microphone.

Audio and Video

Audio was captured from both participants with stage microphones (HSE-150/SK) attached to IMG Stageline EMA-1 adapters and sampled by ESI Maya22 audio interfaces at 44100 Hz. Video was captured by webcams (Logitech C925e; 1080p resolution, 30 frames per second, 78 degrees visual angle) placed on the top of the screens.

Eye Tracking

Participants were equipped with a wearable eye tracker (Pupil Core, Pupil Labs GmbH, Berlin, Germany). This eye tracker has two cameras, the so-called “world camera” recording the scene seen by the participant, and the “eye camera” recording the diameter of the right pupil and the gaze location of the right eye. The sampling rate was 60 Hz for the world camera, and 120 Hz for the eye camera (see further details in Appendix *Eye Tracking*).

Motion Capture

For motion capture, an inertial motion capture system was used (Perception Neuron 32 System, Noitom Ltd., Beijing, China) with 11 sensors (each containing an accelerometer, a magnetometer, and a gyroscope) on the upper-body. The sampling rate was 120 Hz. The Axis Neuron software was used to read sensor data and to derive positions and kinetic measures of the body parts.

Assessing conversation quality in the Free Conversation

Obtaining an adequate measure of conversation quality can be difficult, and there are no clear standards to assess conversation quality in spontaneous face-to-face communication. To have a more comprehensive view of conversation quality we 1) collected subjective evaluations from the participants themselves immediately after completing the Free Conversation task (henceforth will be referred to as internal evaluation of communication outcome) and 2) we recruited independent raters to evaluate the conversations using a set of questionnaires (henceforth will be referred to as external evaluation of communication outcome).

The participant questionnaire (11 items) contained statements about the other player (e.g. “I like my partner”, “I feel like my partner and I were in sync during the previous task”, “During the previous task, I often disagreed with my partner”) and about the task and the conversation in general (e.g. “The previous task was pleasant/enjoyable”, “I think that the previous conversation was smooth and natural”). A 7-point Likert scale was used for each questionnaire item. Exploratory factor analysis revealed no well-defined factors within the questionnaire, therefore, individual items were used in the statistical analyses (see English translations of all items in Table 1 with the original Hungarian items in Appendix *Assessing conversation quality in the Free Conversation* Table A2).

For the external evaluations, 8 university students were recruited in total, and each conversation was evaluated by at least 2 raters (chosen randomly). All raters received two briefing sessions, where instructions were given to them about the questionnaires and what each item was designed to measure. Raters watched the video recordings of the conversations with both participants' camera feeds juxtaposed next to each other and were given full control over stopping and restarting the recordings. Upon completion of the recording, raters were given a questionnaire with 9 items assessing the quality of the conversation and participants' relationship (for the list of English translated items see Table 2 with the original Hungarian items in Appendix *Assessing conversation quality in the Free Conversation* Table A3). A 7-point Likert scale was used for each item. Raters were blind to the condition manipulations. To assess inter-rater agreement, intraclass correlations (ICC) and mean absolute differences (MAD) were calculated between evaluations of the 2 raters per each conversation. For the conversations, where ICC values were lower than 0.4 and MAD values were higher than 1.5 ($n = 16$), we asked a third rater to evaluate the conversation. Then, inter-rater agreements were calculated again for these conversations (for all possible pairings of the 3 raters) and the final mean evaluation for each of these conversations were calculated by averaging the two raters with the highest agreement score; in the case of only two evaluations, the evaluations were also averaged.

Despite receiving prior training, individual differences in “rating style” can still pose a problem. To account for this, we used a z-scoring method to standardize the evaluations using

the following formula: $(Rater1_i - Rater1_{MEAN}) / Rater1_{SD}$ where $Rater1_i$ denotes Rater1's evaluation of that item, $Rater1_{MEAN}$ denotes the mean evaluation for that particular item by Rater1 (from all conversations), and $Rater1_{SD}$ denotes the standard deviation of the evaluations for that item given by Rater1 (again, from all conversations).

The correlation between items of the external evaluation questionnaire and participant questionnaire items are shown in Appendix *Data Acquisition* Fig A2. The correlations among external evaluation questionnaire items are shown in Appendix *Data Acquisition* Fig A3. The correlations among participant evaluation questionnaire items are shown in Appendix *Data Acquisition* Fig A4.

Table 1. Internal evaluation of communication outcome. MEAN and absolute DIFFERENCE were calculated from responses on 7-point Likert scales.

Variable name	Questionnaire items in English and indication of how the Likert scale values for the pair were aggregated
Perceived_Difficulty	I think that the previous task was difficult. - MEAN
Naturalness_of_Conversation	I think that the previous conversation was smooth and natural. - MEAN
Rapport	My partner and I were on the same page during the previous task. - MEAN
Liking	I like my partner. - MEAN
Disagreement	During the previous task, I often disagreed with my partner. - MEAN
Perceived_Synchrony	I feel like my partner and I were in sync during the previous task. - MEAN
Difference_in_Leading	I was leading the conversation during the previous task. - DIFFERENCE
Pleasantness_of_Conversation	The previous task was enjoyable. - MEAN
Surprisal_of_Behavior	My partner's behavior was surprising during the previous task. - MEAN
Predictability_of_the_Partner	My partner was predictable during the previous conversation. - MEAN
Willingness_to_Continue	I would gladly continue the conversation with my partner. - MEAN

Table 2. External evaluations of communication outcome.

Variable name	Questionnaire items in English
Naturalness_of_Conversation	The conversation was smooth and natural.
Equal_Participation	The participants contributed equally to the conversation.
Equal_Leading	The conversation was led by both partners in equal proportion.
Attention_to_Partner	The participants paid attention to one another.
Agreement	The participants mostly agreed with each other.

Pleasantness_of_Conversation	The participants enjoyed the conversation.
Willingness_to_Continue	The participants would have gladly continued the conversation.
Openness	The participants disclosed a lot about themselves and opened up to one another.
Overall_Quality	Overall it was a good conversation.

Measures Assessing Interpersonal Coordination (IC)

Gaze Coordination

Pupil diameter and gaze position within the picture recorded by the world camera was estimated using the automatic 3D pupil detection and gaze mapping algorithms implemented in the Pupil Capture (version 3.4.0) software (Kassner et al., 2014). Preprocessing of the raw pupil diameter data was necessary to correct for data loss due to blinks and other measurement artifacts. This preprocessing included confidence thresholding, diameter thresholding, filtering based on standard deviation, spike removal, removal of small clusters of data points, linear interpolation, and low-pass filtering (see further details in Appendix *Gaze Coordination*). After preprocessing, the amount of discarded pupil diameter samples was estimated for both interlocutors to calculate the number of data points where pupil diameter samples of both interlocutors were acceptable simultaneously. The group-level mean ratio of acceptable paired pupil diameter samples (number of data points where pupil diameter samples of both interlocutors were acceptable simultaneously divided by the total number of pupil samples during the conversation) was 28.64% (SD = 16.04%). Considering this low ratio, pupil size coordination was not estimated and gaze coordination was only assessed by the asymmetry of the two interlocutors' tendency to look at the partner's face (which does not require that the gaze data of the two interlocutors are acceptable simultaneously). The group-level mean ratio of acceptable pupil diameter samples (calculated for each individual separately, not paired) was 54.08% (SD = 19.39%). To estimate the participants' tendency to look at the partner's face, the partner's face was detected using the OpenFace toolkit (Baltrušaitis et al., 2016) on video frames of the world camera. Then, the number of valid gaze positions (corresponding to acceptable pupil samples) on the partner's face relative to the total number of valid gaze positions was calculated ("Looking at face ratio") for both interlocutors. Finally, the absolute difference of the two interlocutors' "Looking at face ratio" values was calculated as a measure of the asymmetry of the two interlocutors' tendency to look at the partner's face.

Motion Coordination

In the current study, motion coordination between the two interlocutors was analyzed based on both head motion and full body (excluding the head) motion. For head motion, motion coordination was estimated by the magnitude squared wavelet coherence (Fujiwara and Daibo, 2016) of the motion energy (calculated as the squared velocity) of the two participant's heads. For full body motion, the same wavelet coherence-based approach was applied on the sum of motion energy of the participant's shoulders, arms, forearms, hands, and trunk. To calculate the

squared velocity, the derivative of position with respect to time was computed and squared separately along the x, y, z directions. Finally, squared velocities along the x, y, z directions were summed, and magnitude squared wavelet coherence (Morlet wavelets, 12 voices per octave) of the two motion energy signals was computed (either for the two heads or for the two full body summed energies). The magnitude-squared wavelet coherence characterizes the correlation between signals in the time-frequency plane. In the current study, coherence values were averaged over time in a turn-taking-base manner. First, turn-takings were selected where the duration of both interlocutors' turns was at least 3 s and the overlap between the two interlocutors' speech did not reach 10%. Next, the longer of the two turns was truncated to the length of the shorter one and magnitude squared wavelet coherence of the two motion energy signals corresponding to the two turns was calculated, and averaged over time. If the truncated turn length was longer than 3 s (and at least 4.5 s), magnitude squared wavelet coherence was calculated in windows with 3 s length and 50 % overlap. Coherence values corresponding to these windows were averaged to have one single coherence value at each frequency for the given turn-taking. The minimum turn length of 3 s was selected based on the resolution of frequency analysis, and the distribution of turn lengths in our data set. The epoch length of 3 s contains at least three cycles of oscillations above 1 Hz, which is a recommended number for synchrony estimation (Cohen, 2014), but theoretically enables the investigation of frequencies above 0.33 Hz. By applying the minimum turn length threshold of 3 s, 43.25% of all turns were kept, containing 58.43% of all data corresponding to turns (excluding periods of silence). The minimum turn length of 3 s resulted in a compromise between keeping a sufficient number of turns representative for a given conversation and having a window length enabling the analysis of low-frequency coherence. For the analysis of frequency, the concept of pseudo pairs was used (see *Validation of Coordination Measures*). Frequency bands were identified where real pairs showed significantly higher motion coherence compared to pseudo pairs using the cluster-based nonparametric statistical test (Maris and Oostenveld, 2007). Within the identified frequency band, motion coherence values were averaged over frequency. For head motion, the frequency band between 2.75 - 4.15 Hz emerged as showing significantly higher coherence for real pairs compared to pseudo pairs. For full body motion, the cluster-based nonparametric statistical test did not yield any frequency band showing significantly higher coherence for real pairs than for pseudo pairs. Note that interlocutors could only see the head of their partner through the video.

Prosodic Coordination and Coordination in the Structure of Speech

Audio streams (stored separately for each participant) underwent minimal preprocessing to remove noise and crosstalk from the other lab and correct for occasional deviations in sampling rates. An automated speech transcriber trained on a large Hungarian corpora (BEA Speech Transcriber - BEAST, Mihajlik et al., 2022) was used to generate transcripts from the audio recordings. Transcription errors and missing segments (including the marking of laughs, hesitations and hummings) in the transcripts were then manually checked and corrected by trained university students and research assistants.

Precise speech on- and offset values were obtained using the Silero Voice Activity Decoder (Silero-VAD) model (Silero Team, 2024) in conjunction with the corrected transcripts. The final speech time series data were sampled at 200 Hz. Pitch and voice intensity values

were then calculated using Parselmouth (version 0.4.4) (Jadoul et al., 2018), a Python library for Praat (Boersma & Weenink, 2021). Speech rate was calculated as the number of syllables per number of samples. Backchannels, pauses and interruptions were automatically detected using the speech time series (see Di Stasi, 2024 for a similar approach).

As participants had already interacted for approximately 30-60 minutes (during the BG task) by the time they reached the Free Conversation task we defined prosodic coordination as global and local proximity instead of convergence following Levitan and Hirschberg's (2011) framework. Meaning, proximity captures the overall similarity in a given feature (signaling that alignment had already happened), whereas convergence indicates the degree to which a feature becomes more similar over time. For local, turn-based measures of proximity, we selected every speech turn that 1) lasted at least 3 s in duration, 2) was followed by a speech turn by the other interlocutor and 3) during which overlap from the other speaker did not reach a 10% threshold. Then, for each selected speech turn, we calculated the median value of a given feature and calculated the absolute differences between successive turn values pertaining to different speakers. Finally, absolute difference values were averaged to obtain a single measure of coordination on a given feature. For a full description of each variable describing prosodic coordination and coordination in the structure of speech see Table 3.

Linguistic Coordination

To assess linguistic coordination, we constructed a text corpus from the recorded conversations and subjected it to a multi-step preprocessing pipeline. The corpus underwent word and sentence tokenization, lemmatization, and part-of-speech (POS) tagging using the EMTSV (EmMorph Text Structure Validator) tool (Simon & Váradi, 2022). Following NLP conventions (Nitin & Damerou, 2010), word tokenization segmented the text into discrete words, and sentence tokenization identified sentence boundaries. Lemmatization reduced each word to its base form, grouping inflected variants, while POS tagging assigned each word to a grammatical category (e.g., verb, noun, adjective).

Two lemmatized versions of the corpus were produced: a raw corpus containing all lemmata without filtering, and a filtered corpus from which punctuation marks, humming, hesitation, and laughter were removed. For both versions, we retained the lemmata as well as the POS tags, resulting in four datasets in total (raw lemmata, filtered lemmata, raw POS, filtered POS). These parallel datasets were necessary because some linguistic variables could only be meaningfully derived from the raw corpora (e.g., paralinguistic features), while others required the filtered corpora (e.g., POS-based categories, where punctuation or paralinguistic items would otherwise distort the distributions). During manual review of the automatically generated POS output, we found that EMTSV distinguishes only present and past tense. Future-tense lemmas (e.g., *will be*, *will*) were therefore manually corrected, and a new POS tag labeled "FUTURE" was introduced.

Subsequently, we performed automated detection of linguistic features. Sentiment and emotion analysis were conducted on the sentence-tokenized corpus. Sentiment analysis, using the NYTK huBERT-based model (NYTK/sentiment-ohb3-hubert-hungarian) (Laki & Yang, 2023), classified each sentence within a conversational turn as positive, negative, or neutral. Since turns could comprise multiple sentences, each received individual sentiment labels, potentially yielding multiple labels per turn. Emotion analysis, conducted with a fine-tuned Hungarian

RoBERTa-based model (Üveges & Ring, 2023), assigned each turn to one category—happiness, sadness, disgust, anger, fear, or no emotion—regardless of sentence count. Both sentiment and emotion outputs were stored separately.

For each of the 334 participants, we calculated the relative frequency of all linguistic variables, using the appropriate dataset depending on the variable in question. Non-lexical elements (humming, laughter, hesitation) and questions were normalized against the total number of raw lemmata, since the raw corpus preserved all tokens including these phenomena. In contrast, grammatical categories such as verb, noun, adjective, numeral, adverb, pronoun, postposition, preverb, article, conjunction, interjection, determiner, verb tense (present, past, future), conditional mood, and person markers (first, second, third person in singular and plural) were normalized against the total number of filtered lemmata, as punctuation and paralinguistic items would otherwise bias the counts (all paralinguistic items were tagged as nouns by EMTSV). The frequency of function words (adverbs, pronouns, postpositions, articles, preverbs, conjunctions, interjections, determiners, and personal markers) was likewise computed relative to the filtered corpus.

Emotion categories (happiness, sadness, anger, disgust, fear, and no emotion) were normalized by the number of conversational turns, since emotions were identified at the turn level and each turn received a single label. Sentiment categories (positive, negative, neutral) were normalized by the total number of sentiment labels, because a conversational turn could contain multiple sentences and therefore multiple sentiment labels.

Lexical diversity was calculated by dividing the number of unique lemmata by the total number of filtered lemmata. Average word count was obtained by dividing the total number of filtered lemmata by the number of conversational turns. Finally, we computed the speech amount between interlocutors as the proportion of an individual’s filtered lemmata relative to the sum of both speakers’ filtered lemmata.

Linguistic coordination was characterized by composite variables calculated as the Euclidean distance between the interlocutors in a vector space spanned by selected individual variables. Before calculating the Euclidean distance, individual variables were scaled by their corresponding overall relative frequency in the corpus to prevent numerically larger variables dominating the composite variables. Table 3 presents the elements of the composite variables.

Variables included in the statistical models set up to predict communication success (see next section) are summarized in Table 3. Each variable was established separately for each pair of participants. Correlations between these predictor variables are shown in Appendix Measures Assessing IC Fig. A5.

Table 3. Predictor variables for modeling communication success.

Type	Name	Definition
Gaze coordination	Looking_at_Face_Difference	Absolute difference between the interlocutors in the number of valid gaze positions on the partner’s face relative to the total number of valid gaze positions.
Motion coordination	Motion_Coordination	Magnitude squared wavelet coherence between the head motion energy signals of the interlocutors.

Prosodic coordination	Local_Proximity_Pitch	Absolute difference between the turn-based median pitch values of the interlocutors, corresponding to turn-takings, averaged over all turn-takings after weighted by turn length.
	Local_Proximity_Pitch_Range	Absolute difference between the turn-based pitch ranges (IQR) of the interlocutors, corresponding to turn-takings, averaged over all turn-takings after weighted by turn length.
	Local_Proximity_Intensity	Absolute difference between the turn-based median intensity values of the interlocutors, corresponding to turn-takings, averaged over all turn-takings after weighted by turn length.
	Local_Proximity_Speech_Rate	Absolute difference between the turn-based speech rates (number of syllables divided by turn length) of the interlocutors, corresponding to turn-takings, averaged over all turn-takings after weighted by turn length.
	Global_Proximity_Pitch	Absolute difference between the mean speech pitch of the interlocutors.
	Global_Proximity_Pitch_Range	Absolute difference between the overall pitch range (IQR) of the interlocutors.
	Global_Proximity_Intensity	Absolute difference between the mean speech intensity of the interlocutors.
	Global_Proximity_Speech_Rate	Absolute difference between the overall speech rates (overall number of syllables divided by total time spent speaking) between the interlocutors.
Conversation structure coordination	Local_Proximity_Backchannel_No	Absolute difference between the turn-based backchannel response (shorter than 1 s speech segments) numbers of the interlocutors, corresponding to turn-takings, averaged over all turn-takings after weighted by turn length.
	Local_Proximity_Pause_No	Absolute difference between the turn-based pause numbers of the interlocutors, corresponding to turn-takings, averaged over all turn-takings after weighted by turn length. Pauses were defined as short, at least 0.2 s silences in a speaker's turn.
	Local_Proximity_Pause_to_Speech	Absolute difference between the turn-based pause to speech ratio (in minutes) of the interlocutors, corresponding to turn-takings, averaged over all turn-takings after weighted by turn length. Pauses were defined as short, at least 0.2 s silences in a speaker's turn.
	Local_Proximity_Response_Time	Absolute difference between the turn-based response times of the interlocutors, corresponding to turn-takings, averaged over all turn-takings after weighted by turn length.
	Local_Proximity_Interruption	Absolute difference between the turn-based binary interruption value (yes or no, at least 0.5 s overlap of speech at turn ends) of the interlocutors, corresponding to turn-takings, averaged over all turn-takings after weighted by turn length.
	Local_Proximity_Turn_Length	Absolute difference between the turn lengths of the interlocutors, corresponding to turn-takings, averaged over all turn-takings after weighted by turn length.
	Local_Proximity_Pause_Rate	Absolute difference between the turn-based pause number per minute of the interlocutors, averaged over all turn-takings after weighted by turn length. Pauses were defined as short, at least 0.2 s silences in a speaker's turn.

	Local_Proximity_Backchannel_Rate	Absolute difference between the turn-based backchannel response rates (shorter than 1 s speech segments per minute) of the interlocutors, corresponding to turn-takings, averaged over all turn-takings after weighted by turn length.
	Global_Proximity_Backchannel_No	Absolute difference between the overall backchannel response (shorter than 1 s speech segments) numbers of the interlocutors.
	Global_Proximity_Backchannel_Rate	Absolute difference between the overall backchannel response rates (shorter than 1 s speech segments per minute) of the interlocutors.
	Global_Proximity_Pause_No	Absolute difference between the overall pause numbers of the interlocutors. Pauses were defined as short, at least 0.2 s silences in a speaker's turn.
	Global_Proximity_Pause_to_Speech	Absolute difference between the overall pause to speech ratio (in minutes) of the interlocutors. Pauses were defined as short, at least 0.2 s silences in a speaker's turn.
	Global_Proximity_Response_Time	Absolute difference between the overall mean response times of the interlocutors.
	Global_Proximity_Interruption	Absolute difference between the overall interruption rates (at least 0.5 s overlap of speech at turn ends, per minute) of the interlocutors.
	Global_Proximity_Turn_Length	Absolute difference between the overall mean turn lengths of the interlocutors.
	Global_Proximity_Pause_Rate	Absolute difference between the overall mean pause number per minute of the interlocutors. Pauses were defined as short, at least 0.2 s silences in a speaker's turn.
Linguistic_Coordination	Global_Proximity_Lexical_Diversity	Absolute difference between the interlocutors in the number of unique lemmata divided by the total number of filtered lemmata.
	Global_Proximity_Word_Count	Absolute difference between the interlocutors in the total number of filtered lemmata divided by the number of conversational turns.
	Global_Proximity_Speech_Amount	Absolute difference between the interlocutors in the proportion of an individual's filtered lemmata relative to the sum of both speakers' filtered lemmata.
	Global_Proximity_Affect	Euclidean distance between the interlocutors in the vector space spanned by emotion categories (happiness, sadness, anger, disgust, fear, and no emotion), and sentiment categories (positive, negative, neutral).
	Global_Proximity_Word_Class	Euclidean distance between the interlocutors in the vector space spanned by word classes (verb, noun, adjective, numeral, adverb, pronoun).
	Global_Proximity_Function_Words	Euclidean distance between the interlocutors in the vector space spanned by function words (pronouns, postpositions, articles, preverbs, conjunctions, interjections, determiners, and negation).
	Global_Proximity_Tense	Euclidean distance between the interlocutors in the vector space spanned by verb tense (present, past, future), and conditional mood.

	Global_Proximity_Person_Markers	Euclidean distance between the interlocutors in the vector space spanned by person markers (first, second, third person in singular and plural).
	Global_Proximity_Non_Lexical	Euclidean distance between the interlocutors in the vector space spanned by non-lexical elements (humming, laughter, hesitation), and questions.
Manipulation	Condition	Experimental condition.
Demographics	Age_Difference	Absolute age difference between the interlocutors.
	Mean_Age	Mean age of the interlocutors.

Statistical Analysis

Data Preparation

Variables measuring the absolute difference between interlocutors were log-transformed to address skewness in the data. 19 pairs had missing motion data (13 pairs in the Baseline condition, 5 pairs in the Unfamiliar condition, 1 pair in the Unimodal condition). Pairs with missing motion data were omitted from the analyses requiring the missing data.

Validation of Coordination Measures

The first step of the statistical analysis was the comparison of real and pseudo pairs for each tested measure of coordination (see Table 3, except for the Manipulations and the Demographics sections of the table). Pseudo pairs are random pairings of participants, who did not participate in the same experimental session and thus did not have the conversation together. That is, they had the conversation in the same context, but with a different partner. Thus, if some measure significantly differs between real pairs and pseudo pairs, it reflects coordination of the given measure due to the actual interaction during the experimental session, as opposed to general contextual commonalities. Therefore, pseudo-pairs can be considered a baseline for synchrony measures. Pseudo pairs were restricted to being selected from the same condition (Baseline, Unfamiliar, Unimodal, Competitive): a recording of a given participant was paired only with recordings of individuals participating in the same condition. Real pairs and pseudo pairs were compared with one-tailed random permutation t-tests (Janssen, 1997), with an alpha-level of 0.05 and 10^5 permutations (with `Mkinfer 1.2` in R; Kohl, 2024). For the variable `Global_Proximity_Speech_Amount`, two-tailed test was used, because one interlocutor could increase his/her relative speech amount only if the partner's relative speech amount decreased, therefore it could not be assumed that real pairs would show smaller differences in this variable than pseudo pairs. For the variable `Motion_Coordination`, one could assume that real pairs would show larger coherence between the interlocutors than pseudo pairs, because, unlike the other IC variables, this variable is not based on difference between the interlocutors; rather it assesses the coordination between them. Holm's method was applied to the significance values in order to control the family-wise error rate (FWER; Holm, 1979). Only measures surviving the validation, i.e. showing significantly different values for real pairs compared to pseudo pairs, were included in the statistical model below.

Testing the Relationships between Coordination and Outcome Variables

We tested the effects of the manipulation, demographic, and the surviving coordination variables (see previous section) on the communication outcome variables (Table 1 and Table 2). Due to the large number of predictor variables, LASSO selection (Helwig, 2017) preceded fitting a generalized linear model (GLM, with `lm` in R, R Core Team, 2025) to the full data set; one model for each outcome variable. Statistically significant (alpha-level 0.05) predictors are reported with the effect sizes estimated by f^2 (Lorah, 2018).

Testing the Relationships between Objective Outcomes of the BG and Outcome Variables of the Free Conversation

Participants in the Free Conversation task had already had a history of interaction with their partner during the BG rounds. Therefore, as an additional analysis, we tested the relationship between BG outcome (objective and subjective) and communication success (external and internal evaluations) in the Free Conversation.

In the BG, five objective outcome measures were defined (Table 4). For each BG outcome variable, the average of the first three rounds was used for each pair and only those pairs were considered who played at least 3 rounds (only 5 pairs played less than 3 rounds). These measures were tested as predictor variables of internal and external evaluations of communication outcome in the Free Conversation fitting a GLM for each outcome variable; due to the low number of predictors, no LASSO selection was computed.

Table 4. Objective communication outcome measures of the BG.

Type	Name	Definition
Communication success	Mean_Wealth_Increase	Increase of wealth relative to the initial wealth (averaged across players).
	Difference_in_Wealth_Increase	Absolute difference between the players in increase of wealth relative to the initial wealth.
Communication efficacy	Mean_Goal_Time	Time spent to collect all must-have tokens (averaged across players).
	Difference_in_Goal_Time	Absolute difference between players in time spent to collect all must-have tokens.
	Total_Time	Time spent on the BG.

The relationship between subjective outcome measures of the BG and evaluations (internal or external) of communication outcome in the Free Conversation is illustrated by a correlation matrix.

Results

Interpersonal Coordination: Real vs. Pseudo Pair Comparisons

While not all coordination variables survived the validation step, we found significantly different IC for real pairs compared to pseudo pairs in all of the categories of the coordination variables (Table 5). As all variables except for Motion_Coordination were log-transformed before the statistical analysis, Table 5 shows both the original mean and standard deviation (upper) and the transformed mean and standard deviation (lower).

Altogether, 15 of the 35 IC variables survived the comparison between real and pseudo pairs (see Table 5), including the variables Global_Proximity_Speech_Amount and Motion_Coordination, where larger values for real than pseudo pairs was in line with the expected direction of the effects - see the *Validation of Coordination Measures* subsection.

Table 5. Results of the permutation tests comparing real and pseudo pairs for IC variables.

For variables, where a transformation was applied before statistical analysis, the upper value shows the original mean and standard deviation (SD), the lower value shows the transformed mean and SD. The direction of the effect is shown as P[seu] > / < R[eal] or P > / < R; see the *Validation of Coordination Measures* subsection for those variables for which an explanation is needed to interpret the statistical finding. * - $p < 0.05$, ** - $p < 0.01$, *** - $p < 0.001$

Variable name	Effect size (Cohen's <i>d</i>)	Mean (SD) real	Mean (SD) pseudo	Direction of the effect	Significance
Looking_at_Face_Difference	-0.233	0.197 (0.164) -1.359 (0.540)	0.235 (0.178) -1.234 (0.539)	P>R	**
Motion_Coordination	0.182	0.200 (0.018)	0.195 (0.023)	P<R	**
Local_Proximity_Pitch_Range	-0.266	1.125 (0.685) 0.048 (0.569)	1.290 (0.745) 0.191 (0.537)	P>R	**
Global_Proximity_Pitch_Range	-0.196	0.802 (0.853) -0.505 (0.903)	0.998 (1.016) -0.321 (0.942)	P>R	*
Local_Proximity_Backchannel_No	-0.256	2.062 (1.857) 0.503 (0.727)	2.414 (2.088) 0.678 (0.681)	P>R	*
Global_Proximity_Backchannel_No	-0.365	15.168 (15.054) 2.081 (1.431)	20.185 (17.909) 2.522 (1.197)	P>R	***
Global_Proximity_Backchannel_Rate	-0.247	2.019 (1.608) 0.412 (0.916)	2.653 (2.111) 0.649 (0.961)	P>R	**
Global_Proximity_Interruption	-0.679	11.192 (10.645) 1.827 (1.397)	20.570 (16.595) 2.600 (1.126)	P>R	***
Global_Proximity_Response_Time	-0.231	38.734 (36.693) 3.168 (1.221)	49.899 (47.212) 3.434 (1.149)	P>R	*
Global_Proximity_Affect	-0.271	2.567 (1.543) 0.847 (0.508)	2.933 (1.602) 0.984 (0.503)	P>R	**
Global_Proximity_Non_Lexical	-0.319	1.859 (1.035) 0.540 (0.521)	2.121 (1.015) 0.692 (0.474)	P>R	**

Global_Proximity_Person_Markers	-0.221	1.788 (1.258) 0.479 (0.532)	1.981 (1.228) 0.593 (0.514)	P>R	*
Global_Proximity_Speech_Amount	0.464	0.179 (0.129) -1.382 (0.468)	0.126 (0.093) -1.570 (0.401)	P<R	***
Global_Proximity_Tense	-0.327	1.233 (0.638) 0.178 (0.485)	1.466 (0.770) 0.335 (0.483)	P>R	***
Global_Proximity_Word_Class	-0.273	0.504 (0.230) -0.569 (0.358)	0.577 (0.297) -0.466 (0.378)	P>R	**

Predicting External Evaluations of Communication Outcome

The above described 15 variables (Table 5) were entered into the LASSO selection and subsequent GLM models of the external evaluations of communication outcome (Table 2), along with the demographic and manipulation-related variables (Table 3). We found that only 4 of the IC variables emerged as significant predictors for the external evaluation measures. Significant relationships are illustrated as a network in Fig. 2.

Global_Proximity_Speech_Amount negatively affected the Equal_Participation item ($p < 0.001$, $f^2 = 0.162$), which shows that with increasing difference in speech amount the equality of participating in the conversation decreased. Global_Proximity_Non_Lexical variable negatively affected a wide range of outcomes. Specifically, it emerged as a significant negative predictor for the Naturalness_of_Conversation ($p < 0.001$, $f^2 = 0.102$), Equal_Leading ($p < 0.001$, $f^2 = 0.077$), Attention_to_Partner ($p < 0.01$, $f^2 = 0.046$), Pleasantness_of_Conversation ($p < 0.001$, $f^2 = 0.108$), Willingness_to_Continue ($p < 0.001$, $f^2 = 0.112$) and Overall_Quality ($p < 0.001$, $f^2 = 0.083$) items. That is, the lower the difference between partners in the use of non-lexical elements of speech (humming, hesitation, laugh) and in the use of questions, the higher the pair scored on the above mentioned items of the external evaluation. We found another robust predictor for the external evaluations: Local_Proximity_Backchannel_No positively affected the Naturalness_of_Conversation ($p < 0.001$, $f^2 = 0.179$), Equal_Leading ($p < 0.05$, $f^2 = 0.027$), Pleasantness_of_Conversation ($p < 0.001$, $f^2 = 0.123$), Willingness_to_Continue ($p < 0.001$, $f^2 = 0.109$), Openness ($p < 0.001$, $f^2 = 0.087$), and the Overall_Quality ($p < 0.001$, $f^2 = 0.131$) items. This means that the higher the differences in the turn-by-turn use of backchannels the higher the scores of these external evaluation items. The fourth significant IC predictor was the Motion_Coordination variable. This variable positively affected the Naturalness_of_Conversation ($p < 0.05$, $f^2 = 0.041$) and the Pleasantness_of_Conversation ($p < 0.05$, $f^2 = 0.034$) ratings. This demonstrates that the higher the coordination of head movements, the more the conversation between the interlocutors felt natural and enjoyable from an outside perspective. Finally, we found an effect of Condition on the external outcome variable Agreement ($p < 0.01$, $f^2 = 0.086$) and Openness ($p < 0.001$, $f^2 = 0.117$). Specifically, our results showed that in the Competitive condition participants seemed to agree more and were less likely to open up to their partner according to the external raters. GLM results including the model fit for external evaluations of communication outcome and significant predictor variables are summarized in Appendix *Predicting External Evaluations of Communication Outcome Table A4*.

Figure 2. Graphical illustration of the GLM results for the external evaluation measures of

the conversation and significant predictor variables. Rectangular nodes: external evaluations of communication outcomes. Rounded nodes: significant predictor variables. Edge color denotes the direction of the relationship between the variables (red: positive, blue: negative), edge thickness denotes the effect size (larger effect size corresponds to thicker edges).

Predicting Internal Evaluations of Communication Outcome

IC (surviving the validation phase), demographic, and manipulation variables were included in the models aimed to explain the internal evaluations of communication outcome. Significant relationships are illustrated as a network in Fig. 3.

Three variables relating to linguistic coordination and coordination in the structure of speech predicted items of the participants' own evaluations of communication outcome. Namely, the *Global_Proximity_Non_Lexical* variable was found to negatively affect Rapport ($p < 0.01$, $f^2 = 0.070$) and *Pleasantness_of_Conversation* ($p < 0.05$, $f^2 = 0.025$). That is, pairs who used non-lexical elements and questions in a similar manner (the overall absolute difference between them was smaller), gave higher scores for rapport and pleasantness.

Local_Proximity_Backchannel_No was again a robust predictor of self-reported communication outcome: it positively affected Rapport ($p < 0.001$, $f^2 = 0.080$), Liking ($p < 0.01$, $f^2 = 0.055$), *Perceived_Synchrony* ($p < 0.01$, $f^2 = 0.054$), *Pleasantness_of_Conversation* ($p < 0.01$, $f^2 = 0.049$) and the *Willingness_to_Continue* ($p < 0.05$, $f^2 = 0.040$) items of the internal evaluations. This indicates that the higher the difference was between partners in the use of backchannels locally, the higher they rated these communication outcome items. Additionally, we found that *Global_Proximity_Affect* emerged as a significant positive predictor for Liking ($p < 0.05$, $f^2 = 0.037$), which shows - counterintuitively - that pairs who were more dissimilar in expressing emotional content liked their partner more. We found no significant predictors for the items *Perceived_Difficulty*, *Naturalness_of_Conversation*, *Disagreement*, *Difference_in_Leading*, *Surprisal_of_Behavior* and *Predictability_of_the_Partner* of the internal evaluation questionnaire. GLM results including the model fit for internal evaluations of communication outcome and significant predictor variables are summarized in Appendix *Predicting Internal Evaluations of Communication Outcome* Table A5.

Figure 3. **Graphical illustration of the GLM results for the internal evaluation measures of the conversation and significant predictor variables.** Rectangular nodes: internal evaluations of communication outcomes. Rounded nodes: significant predictor variables. Edge color denotes the direction of the relationship between the variables (red: positive, blue: negative), edge thickness denotes the effect size (larger effect size corresponds to thicker edges). Only outcome variables with significant predictors are shown.

Assessing the effects of BG Outcome on Communication Outcome in the Free Conversation task

The results showed that the objective outcome variables from the BG predicted some of the Free Conversation outcome measures (Table A6). In particular, the Mean_Wealth_Increase variable positively affected the Agreement ($p < 0.05$, $f^2 = 0.041$) score of the internal evaluation and the Naturalness_of_Conversation ($p < 0.05$, $f^2 = 0.041$) item on the external evaluation questionnaire.

In addition, we found that the Difference_in_Goal_Time variable negatively affected the Pleasantness_of_Conversation ($p < 0.05$, $f^2 = 0.043$) and the Willingness_to_Continue ($p < 0.05$, $f^2 = 0.040$) item on the external evaluation, while it positively affected the Difference_in_Leading ($p < 0.05$, $f^2 = 0.041$) and negatively affected the Surprisal_of_Behavior ($p < 0.05$, $f^2 = 0.039$) items of

the internal evaluation questionnaires. GLM results including model fit and significant predictors are summarized in Table A6.

Regarding the relationship between the subjective outcomes of the BG and the outcomes of the Free Conversation, we found that the highest correlations were related to Liking in the BG ($r > 0.5$). Rapport in the BG also showed moderate correlations ($r > 0.25$) with the Free Conversation outcomes. Not surprisingly, this was only true for the internal evaluation of the Free Conversation, the external evaluations showed no such relationship with the BG outcomes. For the full correlation matrix see Appendix *Assessing the effects of BG Outcome on Communication Outcome in the Free Conversation* Figure A6.

References

- Baltrušaitis, T., Robinson, P., & Morency, L. P. (2016, March). Openface: an open source facial behavior analysis toolkit. In *2016 IEEE winter conference on applications of computer vision (WACV)* (pp. 1-10). IEEE.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/wacv.2016.7477553>
- Béres, L., Nagy, P., Pólya, T., Weiss, B., Boncz, Á., & Winkler, I. (2025). Interpersonal coordination in communication: Effects of alignment in multiple modalities on objective and subjective task outcomes. PsyArXiv. doi: 10.31234/osf.io/sxkeh_v1
- Boersma, P., & Weenink, D. (2021). Praat: doing phonetics by computer [Computer program]. Version 6.1.38, retrieved 2 January 2023 from <http://www.praat.org/>.
- Cohen, M. X. (2014). *Analyzing neural time series data: theory and practice*. MIT press.
- Di Stasi, M., Templeton, E., & Quidbach, J. (2024). Zooming out on bargaining tables: Exploring which conversation dynamics predict negotiation outcomes. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 109(7), 1077. <https://doi.org/10.1037/apl0001136>
- Fujiwara, K., & Daibo, I. (2016). Evaluating interpersonal synchrony: Wavelet transform toward an unstructured conversation. *Frontiers in psychology*, 7, 516.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2016.00516>
- Galinsky, A. D., & Mussweiler, T. (2001). First offers as anchors: the role of perspective-taking and negotiator focus. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 81(4), 657.
<https://doi.org/10.1037//0022-3514.81.4.657>
- Helwig, N. E. (2017). Adding bias to reduce variance in psychological results: A tutorial on penalized regression. *The Quantitative Methods for Psychology*, 13(1), 1-19.
<https://doi.org/10.20982/tqmp.13.1.p001>
- Holm, S. (1979). A simple sequentially rejective multiple test procedure. *Scandinavian journal of statistics*, 65-70.
- Janssen, A. (1997). Studentized permutation tests for non-iid hypotheses and the generalized Behrens-Fisher problem. *Statistics & probability letters*, 36(1), 9-21.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0167-7152\(97\)00043-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0167-7152(97)00043-6)
- Jadoul, Y., Thompson, B., & de Boer, B. (2018). Introducing Parselmouth: A Python interface to Praat. *Journal of Phonetics*, 71, 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wocn.2018.07.001>
- Kassner, M., Patera, W., & Bulling, A. (2014, September). Pupil: an open source platform for pervasive eye tracking and mobile gaze-based interaction. In *Proceedings of the 2014 ACM*

international joint conference on pervasive and ubiquitous computing: Adjunct publication (pp. 1151-1160).

<https://doi.org/10.1145/2638728.2641695>

Kohl, M. (2024). Mkinfer: Inferential statistics. R package version 1.2.

<https://github.com/stamats/MKinfer>.

Kret, M. E., & Sjak-Shie, E. E. (2019). Preprocessing pupil size data: Guidelines and code. *Behavior research methods*, 51, 1336-1342.

<https://doi.org/10.3758/s13428-018-1075-y>

Laki L. J., & Yang Z. Gy. (2023). Sentiment Analysis with Neural Models for Hungarian. *Acta Polytechnica Hungarica*, 20(5), 109–128. <https://doi.org/10.12700/aph.20.5.2023.5.8>

Levitan, R., & Hirschberg, J. (2011, August). Measuring acoustic-prosodic entrainment with respect to multiple levels and dimensions. In *Interspeech* (Vol. 2011, pp. 3081-3084).

<https://doi.org/10.21437/interspeech.2011-771>

Lorah, J. (2018). Effect size measures for multilevel models: Definition, interpretation, and TIMSS example. *Large-scale assessments in education*, 6(1), 1-11.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s40536-018-0061-2>

Mathôt, S. (2018). Pupillometry: Psychology, physiology, and function. *Journal of cognition*, 1(1).

<https://doi.org/10.5334/joc.18>

Maris, E., & Oostenveld, R. (2007). Nonparametric statistical testing of EEG-and MEG-data. *Journal of neuroscience methods*, 164(1), 177-190.

Orosz, G., Szabó, G., Berkecz, P., Szántó, Z., & Farkas, R. (2023, August). Advancing Hungarian Text Processing with HuSpaCy: Efficient and Accurate NLP Pipelines. In *International Conference on Text, Speech, and Dialogue* (pp. 58-69). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.

Mihajlik, P., Balog, A., Grácsi, T. E., Kohári, A., Tarján, B., & Mády, K. (2022, June). BEA-Base: A Benchmark for ASR of Spontaneous Hungarian. In *Proceedings of the Thirteenth Language Resources and Evaluation Conference* (pp. 1970-1977).

Simon, É., & Váradi, T. (2022). EMTSV: Magyar morfológiai elemző és annotáló rendszer. *Magyar Nyelvőr*, 146(2), 181–203.

Silero Team, "Silero VAD: pre-trained enterprise-grade voice activity detector (VAD), number detector and language classifier," <https://github.com/snakers4/silero-vad>, 2024.

Nitin, I., & Damerau, F. J. (2010). *Handbook of natural language processing*. Taylor & Francis.

Üveges I., & Ring O. (2023). HunEmBERT: A Fine-Tuned BERT-Model for Classifying Sentiment and Emotion in Political Communication. *IEEE Access*, 11, 60267–60278.

<https://doi.org/10.1109/access.2023.3285536>

Valley, K., Thompson, L., Gibbons, R., & Bazerman, M. H. (2002). How communication improves efficiency in bargaining games. *Games and Economic Behavior*, 38(1), 127-155.

<https://doi.org/10.1006/game.2001.0855>

Appendix

Materials and Methods

Procedure

Table A1. **List of suggested topics for the Free Conversation task.** Original Hungarian version and their English translations.

English translation	Original text in the Hungarian version
How does she/he spends her/his free time, does she/he have a hobby, does she/he do any sports?	“Hogyan tölti a szabadidejét, van valamilyen hobbi, sportol esetleg?”
What does she/he think of studying abroad? Does she/he plan to participate or did she/he already participate in some kind of foreign exchange program (e.g. Erasmus, Campus Mundi, etc.)?	“Mit gondol a külföldön tanulásról? Gondolkozott-e már rajta, esetleg vett részt valamilyen külföldi tanulmányi programban (pl. Erasmus, Campus Mundi, egyéb)?”
Does she/he plan her/his future in Hungary?	“Magyarországon képzele hosszabb távon a jövőjét?”
What does she/he think is the best way to meet new people?	“Szerinte mik a legjobb terepei az ismerkedésnek?”
How active is she/he on social media platforms? What does she/he think about them?	“Mennyire aktív a közösségi média különböző platformjain? Mit gondol ezekről?”
Learning a language - What does she/he think is the best way to do so?	“Nyelvtanulás - Mit gondol, mi a legjobb módja?”
Films, TV shows, novels - Does she/he have a preference? What was the last thing she/he saw/read?	“Filmek, sorozatok, regények - Van preferenciája? Mit nézett/olvasott utoljára?”

Data Acquisition

Materials

The EEG, the motion capture system, and the wearable eye tracker were connected to a data acquisition PC in each laboratory. Separate PCs were responsible for inter-laboratory communication and audiovisual recordings. Audio was transferred between the two laboratories via microphone cables, video frames via USB, and in-game actions via low-latency User Datagram Protocol (UDP) streams (Fig. A1).

Figure A1. Recording signals and connections between the two laboratories.

Eye Tracking

The Pupil Capture software was used to read the video streams coming from the two cameras of the eye tracker and to calculate pupil size and gaze position based on these video streams. The reliability of gaze tracking was quantified for a subset of participants (176 individuals) using the built-in functionality of the Pupil Capture software to measure the accuracy (the average angular offset between fixation locations and the corresponding locations of the fixation targets) and angular precision (the root mean square of the angular distance between successive samples during fixation) of the gaze tracking. The mean value and standard deviation of accuracy was 2.78 ± 0.49 degrees of visual angle, the mean value and standard deviation of precision was 0.19 ± 0.04 degrees of visual angle.

Assessing conversation quality in the Free Conversation

Table A2. Hungarian version of the questionnaire items used as internal evaluation of communication outcome.

Name	Text of the questionnaire items in Hungarian
Perceived_Difficulty	“Nehéznek éreztem az előző feladatot.”

Naturalness_of_Conversation	"Folytonosnak, természetesnek éreztem az előző beszélgetést."
Rapport	"Megtaláltuk a közös hangot a társammal az előző feladat során."
Liking	"Kedvelem a társamat."
Disagreement	"Gyakran fordult elő, hogy nem érttem egyet a társammal az előző feladat során."
Perceived_Synchrony	"Úgy érzem, hogy összhangban voltunk a társammal az előző feladat során."
Difference_in_Leading	"Én irányítottam a beszélgetést az előző feladat során."
Pleasantness_of_the_Conversation	"Kellemes/élvezetes volt az előző feladat."
Surprisal_of_Behavior	"Meglepő volt a társam viselkedése az előző feladat során."
Predictability_of_the_Partner	"A társam kiszámíthatóan játszotta a játékot."
Willingness_to_Continue	"Szívesen folytattam a beszélgetést a társammal."

Table A3. Hungarian version of the questionnaire items used as external evaluation of communication outcome.

Name	Text of the questionnaire items in Hungarian
Naturalness_of_Conversation	"A beszélgetést gördülékenynek, természetesnek éreztem."
Equal_Participation	"A résztvevők egyenlő mértékben vettek részt a beszélgetésben."
Equal_Leading	"A beszélgetést egyenlő mértékben irányították a résztvevők."
Attention_to_Partner	"A résztvevők figyeltek egymásra."
Agreement	"A résztvevők többnyire egyetértettek egymással (tartalmilag)."
Pleasantness_of_Conversation	"A beszélgetés élvezetesnek tűnt a résztvevők számára."
Willingness_to_Continue	"A résztvevők még szívesen folytatták volna a beszélgetést."
Openness	"A résztvevők sokat megmutattak magukból, megnyíltak egymásnak."
Overall_Quality	"Összességében ez egy jó beszélgetés volt."

Figure A2. Correlation between external (rows) and internal (columns) evaluation questionnaire items.

Figure A3. Correlations among external evaluation questionnaire items.

Figure A4. Correlations among internal evaluation questionnaire items.

Measures Assessing IC

Gaze Coordination

Pupil diameter and gaze position were estimated using the automatic 3D pupil detection and gaze mapping algorithms implemented in the Pupil Capture software. We opted for the 3D model as it offers robust pupil detection and compensates for slippage with the disadvantage of lower gaze position accuracy (recommended by Pupil Labs). First, data points where confidence values of pupil detection obtained from the Pupil Capture software were not within the acceptable range (above 0.6) were considered missing. Another filter removed pupil data which fell outside the physiologically feasible range (1.5-9 mm based on Mathôt, 2018) and/or was 3 standard deviations above or below the median pupil diameter.

Certain artifacts ('spikes') caused by blinks can remain in the signal after removing invalid samples based on pupil confidence thresholds (given by the Pupil Capture software). These artifacts are characterized by disproportionately large changes in pupil size – or dilation speeds. Following the guidelines of Kret & Sjak-Shie (2019), spikes were removed using a filter based on the median absolute deviation of the speed of diameter change between successive samples. We used the following formula, where $d[i]$ denotes the pupil size with the

corresponding timestamps $t[i]$, and the dilation speed at each sample $d'[i]$ is then calculated as the maximum absolute change relative to either the preceding or the succeeding sample:

$$d'[i] = \max(| (d[i] - d[i-1]) / (t[i] - t[i-1]) | , | (d[i+1] - d[i]) / (t[i+1] - t[i]) |)$$

Dilation speed outliers were detected using the median absolute deviation (MAD) value, which was calculated from the dilation speed series, and then multiplied by a constant (n) and summed with the median dilation speed:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MAD} &= \text{median}(| d'[i] - \text{median}(d') |), \\ \text{threshold} &= \text{median}(d') + n * \text{MAD} \end{aligned}$$

The constant was set to 3 based on visual examination of the artifacts. The dilation speed filtering method was applied twice to remove any additional dilation speed outliers missed by the first filter (due to for example the clustering of 2 or more outlier samples).

To deal with the remaining noise in the signal before interpolation, we applied an additional filter which removed small clusters of spurious samples ('loners') that were temporally separated from other valid samples. Clusters were labeled 'loners' and were set to invalid if they were surrounded by invalid samples (resulting from previous filtering steps) and had a maximum length of 2 samples. This threshold was chosen as it yielded the best results for removing interpolation spikes (determined by visually inspecting the data). Then, the missing pupil diameter data were linearly interpolated and low-pass filtered (a fifth-order Butterworth low-pass filter with 10 Hz cutoff frequency using two-direction zero-phase filtering).

Correlations of the Predictor Variables

Figure A5. Correlation between predictor variables of communication success (excluding the categorical variable “Condition”).

Results

Predicting External Evaluations of Communication Outcome

Table A4. GLM results for external evaluation measures of the conversation and significant predictor variables.

Output variable	Model fit (R ²)	Input variable	Effect size (f ²)	Direction	p-value
-----------------	-----------------------------	----------------	-------------------------------	-----------	---------

Naturalness_of_Conversation	0.225	Motion_Coordination	0.041	Pos.	<0.05
		Local_Proximity_Backchannel_No	0.169	Pos.	<0.0001
		Global_Proximity_Non_Lexical	0.102	Neg.	<0.001
Equal_Participation	0.289	Global_Proximity_Speech_Amount	0.162	Neg.	<0.0001
Equal_Leading	0.095	Local_Proximity_Backchannel_No	0.027	Pos.	<0.05
		Global_Proximity_Non_Lexical	0.077	Neg.	<0.001
Attention_to_Partner	0.046	Global_Proximity_Non_Lexical	0.046	Neg.	<0.01
Agreement	0.147	Condition	0.086	Pos.	<0.01
Pleasantness_of_Conversation	0.190	Motion_Coordination	0.034	Pos.	<0.05
		Local_Proximity_Backchannel_No	0.123	Pos.	<0.0001
		Global_Proximity_Non_Lexical	0.108	Neg.	<0.001
Willingness_to_Continue	0.162	Local_Proximity_Backchannel_No	0.109	Pos.	<0.0001
		Global_Proximity_Non_Lexical	0.112	Neg.	<0.0001
Openness	0.190	Condition	0.117	Neg.	<0.001
		Local_Proximity_Backchannel_No	0.087	Pos.	<0.001
Overall_Quality	0.160	Local_Proximity_Backchannel_No	0.131	Pos.	<0.0001
		Global_Proximity_Non_Lexical	0.083	Neg.	<0.001

Predicting Internal Evaluations of Communication Outcome

Table A5. GLM results for internal evaluation measures of the conversation and significant predictor variables.

Output variable	Model fit (R ²)	Input variable	Effect size (f ²)	Direction	p-value
Rapport	0.199	Local_Proximity_Backchannel_No	0.080	Pos.	<0.001
		Global_Proximity_Non_Lexical	0.070	Neg.	<0.01
Liking	0.124	Local_Proximity_Backchannel_No	0.055	Pos.	<0.01
		Global_Proximity_Affect	0.037	Pos.	<0.05
Perceived_Synchrony	0.052	Local_Proximity_Backchannel_No	0.054	Pos.	<0.01

Pleasantness_of_Conversation	0.139	Local_Proximity_Backchannel_No	0.049	Pos.	<0.01
		Global_Proximity_Non_Lexical	0.025	Neg.	<0.05
Willingness_to_Continue	0.039	Local_Proximity_Backchannel_No	0.039	Pos.	<0.05

Table A6. GLM results for outcome variables of the Free Conversation (external or internal, as indicated in brackets) and objective communication outcome measures of the BG as significant predictor variables.

Output variable	Model fit (R ²)	Input variable	Effect size (f ²)	Direction	p-value
Agreement (External)	0.069	Mean_Wealth_Increase	0.041	Pos.	<0.05
Pleasantness_of_Conversation (External)	0.059	Difference_in_Goal_Time	0.043	Neg.	<0.05
Willingness_to_Continue (External)	0.061	Difference_in_Goal_Time	0.040	Neg.	<0.05
Naturalness_of_Conversation (Internal)	0.054	Mean_Wealth_Increase	0.041	Pos.	<0.05
Difference_in_Leading (Internal)	0.083	Difference_in_Goal_Time	0.041	Pos.	<0.05
Surprisal_of_Behavior (Internal)	0.056	Difference_in_Goal_Time	0.039	Neg.	<0.05

Assessing the effects of BG Outcome on Communication Outcome in the Free Conversation

Figure A6. **Correlation between evaluations (internal or external) of communication outcome in the Free Conversation and subjective outcome measures of the BG.** X axis depicts the subjective outcome items of the BG, while the Y axis shows the Free Conversation outcomes. On the Y axis, the external evaluation items are marked with red, while internal evaluation items are marked with blue.